

Increasing efficacy of urea in wetland rice cultivation

Syed Nazeer Peeran and S. Natanasabapathy, Soil Science Section, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur 602025, Chingleput Dist., Tamil Nadu, India

Field trials in sandy loam soils for two seasons investigated the efficacy of urea for wetland rice. The experiments were in strip-plot design with 3 main treatments (nitrogen levels, 0, 75, 150 kg/ha)

and 6 subtreatments of mode of urea application.

The efficacy of placement of urea by applicator or through paper ball was pronounced when urea was applied in two doses: 1/2 as placement on the 15th day and 1/2 as topdressing on the 35th day after planting (see table). Between the two methods of placement, the paper ball was more efficacious.

An important feature of urea place-

ment was the saving of about 50% of the fertilizer compared to a conventional method of application (1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressing). The yield of 4.0 to 4.2 t/ha obtained in 1980 navarai with the application of 150 kg N/ha by the conventional method was equal to the yield obtained with application of 75 kg N/ha as 1/2 placement on the 15th day + 1/2 as topdressing on the 35th day after planting. ■

Effect of mode of nitrogen application on rice grain yield. PES, Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India, 1979-80.

Mode of application and N levels ^a	Grain yield (t/ha) for 1979 samba (IR20)				Increase (%) over control	Grain yield (t/ha) for 1980 navarai (TKM9)				Increase (%) over control
	0 N	75 kg N	150 kg N	Mean		0 N	75 kg N	150 kg N	Mean	
T1 = all basal	1.6	2.1	2.2	2.0	100	2.1	3.2	4.0	3.1	100
T2 = 1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressed	1.5	2.0	2.4	2.0	100	2.0	3.5	4.2	3.2	103
T3 = all by applicator 15 DP	1.6	2.2	2.5	2.1	105	2.0	3.5	4.4	3.3	106
T4 = all by paper ball 15 DP	1.6	2.3	2.7	2.2	110	2.0	3.8	4.5	3.4	110
T5 = 1/2 by applicator 15 DP + 1/2 broadcast 35 DP	1.5	2.5	2.8	2.3	115	2.1	3.9	4.6	3.5	113
T6 = 1/2 by paper ball 15 DP + 1/2 broadcast 35 DP	1.6	2.7	2.9	2.4	120	2.2	4.2	4.8	3.1	119
Mean	1.5	2.3	2.6			2.1	3.7	4.4		
% over control	100	153	173			100	176	210		
	<i>F-test</i>		<i>SE</i>	<i>CD</i>		<i>F-test</i>		<i>SE</i>	<i>CD</i>	
Main treatment (levels of N)	S**		0.092	0.319		S**		0.034	0.118	
Subtreatment (mode of N application)	S*		0.083	0.250		S**		0.082	0.246	
<i>Interactions:</i>										
a) Sub at main	NS		0.124	—		NS		0.148	—	
b) Main at sub	NS		0.196	—		NS		0.201	—	

^a DP = days after planting.

Influence of soil water treatments on nutrient availability in soil and yield of dryland rice

R. V. Ghugare, K. R. Sonar, and G. K. Zende, Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science Department, Mahatma Phule Agricultural University (MPAU), Rahuri 413722, Maharashtra, India

A field experiment on a calcareous Vertisol (pH 8.6, CaCO₃ equivalent 9.8%, and organic carbon 0.68%) at MPAU in the 1978 rainy season investigated the effect of soil water treatments on the availability of nutrients in soil and on rice yield. For 15 days before rice was sown the following

soil water treatments were given: dry (no irrigation), saturation (about 6 cm irrigation on alternate days), and submergence (2 irrigations daily). Two rice varieties were compared: Karjat 184 (semidwarf, wetland) and Tuljapur 1 (tall, dryland). Soil moisture conditions were maintained at about yield capacity (dryland conditions) throughout crop growth. Changes in nutrient availability as a result of soil water treatments 5 days before sowing were studied and yields of rice grain and straw were recorded.

The available nitrogen, phosphorus, iron, and manganese supply in the soil (see table) increased with soil-water treatments 15 days before sowing. The availability of those nutrients was

significantly higher in the presowing soil-submergence treatment compared with the soil saturation and control treatments. This increase in nutrient availability might be due to moderately reducing soil conditions as a result of presowing soil submergence (the Eh value decreased from 501 to 362 mV and the pH decreased from 8.6 to 8.0).

Yields of rice grain and straw were significantly higher in the presowing soil water treatments. Yields of the soil submergence treatment 15 days before sowing were significantly higher than those of the control and the soil-saturation treatments. That could be because of the higher supply of nitrogen phosphorus, iron, and manganese in soil

Nutrient availability in soil and rice yield as influenced by presowing soil water treatments (average of 2 varieties).^a Maharashtra, India.

Treatment ^b	Available nutrients in soil (ppm)								Rice yield (t/ha)	
	15th day after soil water treatments				At sowing				Grain	Straw
	Nitro- gen	Phos- phorus	Iron	Man- ganese	Nitro- gen	Phos- phorus	Iron	Man- ganese		
<i>Presowing soil water treatments</i>										
Dry soil	76.6	10.70	2.63	4.58	83.71	11.64	2.89	4.93	2.61	2.87
Soil saturation	94.5	12.94	3.96	7.80	94.92	12.47	4.02	7.88	2.92	3.31
Soil submergence	107.2	13.22	4.78	8.64	97.70	13.05	4.83	8.75	3.12	3.42
“F” test	**	*	**	**	**	**	**	**	*	*
S.E. ±	2.5	0.58	0.28	0.33	1.33	0.19	0.24	0.32	0.11	0.12
C.D. at 5%	7.7	1.75	0.84	1.01	3.99	0.57	0.73	0.96	0.34	0.35
<i>Rice cultivars</i>										
Karjat 184									1.82	2.28
Tuljapur 1	No crop standing as nutrient availability in soil was studied up to sowing of rice.								3.94	4.16
“F” test									**	**
S.E. ±									0.09	0.09
C.D. at 5%									0.28	0.28

^aSignificance at the 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels. ^bInteraction between presowing soil water treatments and rice cultivars was nonsignificant.

during the early growth stages.

The tall, dryland cultivar Tuljapur 1

yielded significantly more grain and straw than Karjat 184. Dryland soil

conditions seem favorable to tall, dryland rice cultivars. ■

Relation of sowing time and seedling age to rice yields during rabi season

R. A. Khan and A. K. Swarnkar, Agronomy Division, M. P. Rice Research Institute, Labhandi, Raipur, India

The sowing time and age of rice seedlings must be adjusted carefully during the rabi season to obtain good seed germination and seedling growth during the initial stages when temperature is low and to facilitate early harvest before the rains begin.

An experiment in the 1978 rabi studied the effect of time of nursery sowing and seedling age on the yield of early-maturing rice varieties with and without foliar application of potash. The design was split plot with three replications. Three nursery sowing dates — 21 December, 28 December, and 4 January 1979 —and two seedling ages at transplanting (6 and 7 weeks) were in the main plots. Allocated each to subplot were two early-maturing semidwarf varieties, R155-2601 and Kalinga 2, and two potash application treatments (no foliar application and 1 foliar application, 1% concentration). Fertilizer was applied to all treatments at 80 kg N, 40 kg P₂O₅, and 30 kg K₂O/ha. Seedlings were

transplanted at a 20- x 10-cm spacing.

The effect of time of sowing on yield was highly significant. Sowing in the first week of January was superior to sowing in the third and fourth weeks of December (see table). That was because of low temperatures in the third week (25.4° C max, 8.2° C min) and the fourth (25.6° C max, and 8.1° C min) of December. The mean maximum and minimum temperatures from 4 to 10

January were 27.3° C and 10.5° C. Seedling age also gave significant differences. The 7-week-old seedlings performed better than the 6-week-old. Interaction between sowing time and seedling age was not significant.

Kalinga 2 gave significantly higher yields than R155-2601. The effect of foliar application of potash was not significant. ■

Effect of time of nursery sowing and seedling age on the yield of early-maturing rice varieties during the rabi season. Raipur, India, 1978–79.

Sowing date	Seedling age (wk)	Yield (t/ha)		
		R155-2601	Kalinga 2	Mean
21 Dec	6	0.92	1.05	0.99
	7	1.12	1.38	1.25
	Mean	1.02	1.22	1.12
28 Dec	6	0.95	1.20	1.08
	7	1.12	1.37	1.25
	Mean	1.04	1.29	1.16
4 Jan	6	1.16	1.53	1.35
	7	1.23	1.92	1.57
	Mean	1.19	1.73	1.46
Mean	6	1.01	1.26	1.14
	7	1.16	1.56	1.36
Overall mean		1.08	1.41	

For comparison of means of 2 sowing dates, CD at 5%
 For comparison of means of 2 seedling ages, CD at 5%
 For interaction (sowing date x seedling age), CD at 5%
 For comparison of means of 2 varieties, CD at 5%

210.
 172.
 not significant
 104.